

Large Language Models on Wikipedia Editing: The Stylistic Mask Effect in a Randomized Controlled Intervention in Health Education

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Abstract. The effects of large language models (LLM) on content, references, and language quality in Wikipedia assignments remain unclear. This randomized controlled study assessed how model assistance influences the quality of Wikipedia edits created by undergraduate audiology students. Thirty-six participants were assigned to two groups: Group 1 (G1) edited without LLM support, and Group 2 (G2) edited with ChatGPT support. Twenty blinded expert reviewers evaluated a sample of 30 texts (15 per group) using a six-item Likert-scale instrument covering Content, References, and Language. Inter-rater reliability was high (Gwet's AC2 = 0.80). The analysis suggests that LLM assistance may lead to a significant improvement in Language ($\beta = 0.400$; $p = 0.023$; Cliff's $\delta = 0.400$). G2 improved by 0.68 ± 0.47 , while G1 improved by 0.28 ± 0.57 . The analysis found no significant differences for Content ($\beta = 0.167$; $p = 0.214$) or References ($\beta = -0.267$; $p = 0.859$), although G2 scores in the latter category trended lower. Output counts were not associated with quality improvement in either group. This asymmetry is proposed as a potential Stylistic Mask Effect. It describes a gap between surface language gains and limited substantive development. LLM assistance appears to risk substituting constructive contribution with linguistic polish.

Keywords. Encyclopedias as Topic; Natural Language Processing; Education, Medical, Undergraduate; Writing; Audiology/education

Introduction

Wikipedia is one of the most widely accessed sources of health information globally. Its medical content receives more unique pageviews than other major online health resources (Smith, 2020; Alibudbud, 2023). This reach makes content quality and accuracy critical for health communication. Patients and professionals increasingly depend on digital platforms for clinical information (Petroni et al., 2023; Moás & Lopes, 2024; Weiner et al., 2019; Morata et al., 2024). Wikipedia operates on a volunteer-based collaborative model that relies on expert input to refine content. This engagement maintains article accuracy and completeness (Chen et al., 2024; Shafee et al., 2017).

The rapid rise of large language models (LLMs) has created concerns in educational and open-knowledge environments (Kasneci et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2025a). Models such as ChatGPT are now widely used by students and patients for information retrieval, text generation, and knowledge synthesis. Despite their widespread adoption, LLM reliability varies significantly in health contexts (Wang et al., 2024; Wei et al., 2024; Chuang et al., 2024; Alanezi, 2024). This trend highlights the need to understand how LLM assistance affects the quality of user-generated content, especially on platforms where verifiability matters (Petroni et al., 2023; Vetter et al., 2025). In educational settings, LLM-supported writing engages students in diverse knowledge production tasks. Studies have reported their use for editing Wikipedia articles (Shao et al., 2024; Brooks et al., 2024).

Research on the effects of LLM assistance on quality in collaborative open-knowledge environments is still limited (Vetter et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2024). Many studies examine how LLMs affect writing quality. However, data remain scarce for digital spaces where thematic depth and source reliability matter (Huang et al., 2025b; Deckelmann, 2023). Although LLMs appear effective for improving language fluency, they cannot produce authoritative knowledge or distinguish between belief and fact. This stems from their nature as stochastic probabilistic systems that generate text based on statistical patterns. LLMs may fail to generate the verifiable references required for evidence-based content. This is a critical limitation for platforms such as Wikipedia and for health dissemination materials (Petroni et al., 2023; Linardon et al., 2025; Chelli et al., 2024). Moreover, continuous reliance on these models can harm self-efficacy, psychological ownership, and the meaningfulness of learning. Dependence on generated content can lower critical thinking. Students may achieve improved linguistic fluency, yet their writing fails to demonstrate substantive development or genuine understanding (Ding et al., 2025; Xing et al., 2025; Monett & Paquet, 2025). This poses a significant risk to health literacy. Patients frequently seek hearing health information online. Inaccurate or poorly sourced content has direct implications for patient safety (Morata et al., 2024).

This study assessed how LLM assistance affects the quality of Wikipedia edits produced by undergraduate audiology students. We assessed language, content, and references independently. Recognizing that LLMs operate primarily at the surface level of text, our exploratory hypothesis

posits that LLM-assisted editing might enhance language quality but fail to improve deeper content or stronger references. This pattern suggests that LLM-assisted writing substitutes stylistic refinement for substantive knowledge production. Such a distinction has direct implications for collaborative writing environments like Wikipedia and their role in health communication.

Methods

This study employs an exploratory randomized controlled educational intervention. It has obtained approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculdade de Odontologia de Bauru, Universidade de São Paulo (process no. 6.823.110). All participants provided informed consent in accordance with Resolution 466/2012 of the Brazilian National Research Ethics Commission. The reporting of this study was oriented by the CONSORT (Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials) and CHART (Chatbot Health Advice studies) guidelines.

Wikipedia Assignment

Forty-four undergraduate students were invited to participate. Eight of them were excluded for failing to complete the Consent Form or other data-collection instruments, resulting in a final sample of 36 participants, aged 18–30 years, comprising 32 women and 4 men. This demographic distribution is typical of audiology degree programs in Brazil. The students were invited as part of an undergraduate clinical course.

Participants were randomly assigned to two groups, G1 and G2, using a computer-based randomization that did not account for baseline factors such as age, gender, or experience. The groups were formed by sequentially splitting pre-randomized identifiers before any contact with participants. G1 (18 students) did not use an LLM for Wikipedia editing, while G2 (18 students) did. There were no sex differences between groups. Participants did not know their group until the activity started. The participants had no practical experience editing on Wikipedia. All participants received training on Wikipedia editing, structured from the Wiki Education's Outreach Dashboard (<https://outreachdashboard.wmflabs.org/training>); training on LLM use covered the fundamentals of artificial intelligence, how language models function, access and use of LLM, ethical considerations and risks, and prompt construction.

Students edited content to improve the assigned article's information quality without strict rules, using individual internet-enabled computers. G1 edited Wikipedia without LLM support. G2 used ChatGPT with free-form, self-selected prompts to maximize validity. No temperature setting was controlled, as the default interface configuration was used. The study focused on the overall effect of LLM availability rather than on specific prompting strategies, with variability in tool use treated as part of the phenomenon. The groups were edited separately in different locations and times, each for 90

minutes. For this study, a Wikipedia contribution is understood as text produced in accordance with the platform's core editorial principles: a neutral point of view and verifiability grounded in reliable, published sources.

Each participant was assigned a unique article from the Portuguese Wikipedia 'Audiology' category (<https://w.wiki/9SKp>), retrieved in September 2025 using the MediaWiki Action API. Articles aligned with the undergraduate audiology course were selected, and quality scores from the LiftWing model were used to classify articles into tiers. A quota sampling based on these tiers ensured that each participant had a distinct article of comparable quality; this approach aims to reduce ceiling and floor effects.

Model Selection

The selected model was OpenAI-ChatGPT (GPT-5, Instant mode). The study was conducted in September 2025 after GPT-5's release in May 2025. The choice was driven by its availability and status as a default interface, enhancing validity by reflecting current user conditions. The research questions concerning the effects of LLM assistance on linguistic and substantive quality remain valid across GPT versions, as the core transformer-based text-generation mechanism has remained consistent across iterations. Edits were limited to Wikipedia sandbox pages (personal draft spaces isolated from the encyclopedia's main space), with contributions identified to the Lusophone Wikipedia community. Before the activity, a notification was posted on the Lusophone Wikipedia community page (Esplanada) to inform volunteer editors of the educational intervention, in accordance with ethical research practice. The intervention took place in Bauru, São Paulo, Brazil.

Content Selection

Wikipedia texts from 36 participants were reduced to 30 (15 per group: G1 and G2) using a computational sampling method based on average word length. The sample size was validated with the finite population correction formula (95% confidence, $p=0.5$, 12% margin of error), resulting in $n=15$ per group. To ensure the texts reflected typical editing behavior and to avoid outliers (very short or very long edits), the absolute difference from each group's median word count was used as the cutoff. The 15 texts closest to the median in each group were selected, excluding the 3 with the greatest deviation (6 total). Extreme word counts were excluded to reduce heterogeneity, as very short edits may indicate disengagement or misunderstanding, and long edits could show pre-existing expertise. Focusing on texts near the median helps analyse typical editing behaviour. This criterion was applied in both groups to preserve randomization. Word count and references added during editing were also compared between groups.

Instrument

A questionnaire (Appendix A) was created to evaluate the quality of Wikipedia articles, consisting of six questions rated on a four-point Likert scale (Poor, Fair, Good, Excellent). Its construction was based on an open-licensed assessment rubric used in educational activities involving (Wiki Education Foundation, 2025; see also <https://w.wiki/8Xzv>). This rubric was selected for its use in Wikipedia educational contexts and its development by the Wikipedia educational community. The instrument is structured across three dimensions with six items. Content: Evaluates thematic scope (Q1), ensuring all relevant aspects are covered, and quality/accuracy (Q2), assessing if the information is current and clearly explained. References: Checks verifiability through citation coverage (Q3) and the reliability of the sources utilized (Q4). Language: Assesses textual mechanics and correctness (Q5) alongside the logical organization and coherence of topics (Q6). The rubric was not originally developed for LLM-assisted content. Its dimensions remain applicable to assess the textual enhancement and the conceptual development of student contributions to Wikipedia.

Data Handling and Descriptive Statistics

Data were retrieved from the original and edited Wikipedia articles and collected using FormsBricks. LibreOffice Calc (v. 26.2.0.3) was used for initial tabulation. Quality improvement was defined as the difference between post-intervention and pre-intervention scores. It was averaged across the two evaluators per article. Descriptive statistics summarised pre- and post-intervention means and standard deviations.

Statistical Analysis

Quality improvement was defined as the difference between post- and pre-intervention scores, averaged across evaluators. Group differences were assessed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, with estimates reported as β ($G2 - G1$) and standard errors (SE). Considering the directional hypothesis that LLM assistance would improve Language more than no-LLM editing ($G2 > G1$), one-tailed p-values (p-OLS) were computed from the t-statistic of the LLM coefficient. The Benjamini-Hochberg adjustment (p-BH; $\alpha = 0.10$, adjusted for exploratory hypothesis) was applied to these one-tailed p-values across the three dimensions (Content, References, Language; $\alpha = 0.10$). Effect sizes were quantified with Cliff's δ ; 95% confidence intervals were obtained by percentile bootstrap with $B = 5,000$ resamples drawn independently of each group. Items within each dimension were averaged into a single composite score prior to analysis. This aligns the analytical unit with the instrument's theoretical structure and attenuate item-level measurement error.

Secondary variables (word count and references added) were examined for normality using Shapiro-Wilk test. Group comparisons used Welch's t-test for normally distributed data and the

Mann-Whitney U test otherwise. Associations between output volume and quality improvement were assessed with Spearman correlations. Statistical significance using $\alpha = 0.05$ for secondary analyses.

Expert Review Panel

Twenty Brazilian researchers, all with doctoral degrees in hearing health, evaluated the Wikipedia articles. The panel was blinded to the editing methods. Each reviewer assessed three to four articles (N=30) from an electronic form. Reviewers received an instructional document describing the tasks and student activities. Each article underwent independent review by two specialists. Inter-rater reliability was calculated using Raw Agreement and Gwet's AC2 with custom neighbour weights for ordinal categories. AC2 was preferred over weighted κ to avoid the kappa paradox in skewed Likert distributions.

Table 1. Inter-Rater Reliability of the Expert Evaluation Panel

Analysis	Raw Agreement	Gwet's AC2
Group 1	92.8%	0.880
Group 2	85.0%	0.844

Content (Q1 and Q2)	98.3%	0.891
References (Q3 and Q4)	86.7%	0.809
Language (Q5 and Q6)	81.7%	0.811

Consistency was moderate to high (Table 1). Gwet's AC2 values ≥ 0.80 indicate strong agreement. Metrics reflect blinded independent assessment by two reviewers per Wikipedia article.

Statistical Power and Reporting Metrics

A post hoc power analysis indicated 56.2% power (95% bootstrap CI: 53.2%-59.4%) to detect a large effect (Cohen's $d = 0.8$) at the final sample size of $n = 15$ per group, estimated by Monte Carlo simulation with 1,000 independent samples under the alternative hypothesis. The proportion of simulated datasets reaching $p < .05$ with a two-sample t-test was taken as the power estimate, and the 95% CI was obtained by bootstrap resampling. The minimum detectable effect for 80% power at $\alpha = 0.05$ was $r \approx 0.47$.

Reproducibility and Software

Although the study was not prospectively registered, all analytical decisions are documented in the deposited code and data to allow independent verification. All statistical analyses were conducted in R

(version 4.4.3) within the RStudio IDE (Posit Software, version 2025.09.2+418). Dataset and code were deposited in the Zenodo repository (10.5281/zenodo.20320536).

Results

The present study evaluated the impact of LLM assistance on the quality of Wikipedia edits by comparing the improvements in scores between students who edited without LLM support (G1) and those who used an LLM (G2). Assessment was based on Content (Q1 and Q2), References (Q3 and Q4), and Language (Q5 and Q6).

Pre-intervention scores were similar between groups, supporting the equivalence achieved by quota sampling based on LiftWing quality tiers. Content baselines were equivalent (G1: 2.98 ± 0.56 ; G2: 2.98 ± 0.51). References baselines were higher in G2 (3.23 ± 0.41) than in G1 (2.98 ± 0.66). Language baselines were lower in G2 (2.78 ± 0.36) than in G1 (2.98 ± 0.64).

Table 2. Editing Quality Improvement

Improvement		β (G2 - G1)	SE	p-OLS ($\alpha=0.05$)	p-BH ($\alpha=0.10$)	Cliff's δ [95% CI]
G1	G2					
Content (Q1 and Q2)						
0.42 ± 0.65	0.58 ± 0.48	+0.167	0.207	0.214	0.321	0.253 [-0.156, 0.658]

References (Q3 and Q4)						
0.25 ± 0.56	-0.02 ± 0.76	-0.267	0.243	0.859	0.859	-0.164 [-0.547, 0.258]

Language (Q5 and Q6)						
0.28 ± 0.57	0.68 ± 0.47	+0.400	0.191	0.023	0.068	0.400 [+0.004, 0.751]

Note. Statistical comparison between groups (G1 and G2). Table reports estimates (β), standard errors (SE), and raw p-values (p-OLS) from Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models. Adjusted p-values (p-BH) were calculated using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure to control for the false discovery rate ($\alpha=0.10$). Effect sizes are reported as Cliff's δ with 95% confidence intervals (CI). Cliff's δ is interpreted as negligible ($|\delta| < 0.147$), small ($0.147 \leq |\delta| < 0.330$), medium ($0.330 \leq |\delta| < 0.474$), or large ($|\delta| \geq 0.474$).

Table 2 shows that editing improvement varied across the evaluated domains. The greatest improvement was observed in the Language dimension, where G2 (0.68 ± 0.47) demonstrated a greater improvement than G1 (0.28 ± 0.57). This difference produced a positive effect size (Cliff's $\delta = 0.400$; 95% CI: +0.004, 0.751), with p-OLS of 0.023 and p-BH of 0.068. Content scores also showed a non-significant positive trend for the LLM-assisted group (G2: 0.58 ± 0.48 and G1: 0.42 ± 0.65 ; p-OLS = 0.214; p-BH = 0.321; Cliff's $\delta = 0.253$). Improvement in the References dimension was marginally lower for G2 (-0.02 ± 0.76) compared to G1 (0.25 ± 0.56), a difference that was not statistically significant (p-OLS = 0.859; p-BH = 0.859).

Group-level differences in text production were examined for two secondary variables: word count and number of references added. The word count reported normality (G1: $W = 0.968$, $p = 0.833$; G2: $W = 0.936$, $p = 0.332$) and differed significantly between groups (Welch's t-test: $t(17.45) = 5.40$, $p < 0.001$). G2 produced longer texts (mean = 649.7 words, $SD = 285.5$; range: 277-1,160) than G1 (mean = 227.8 words, $SD = 101.0$; range: 80-436). The number of references added indicated non-normality (G1: $W = 0.837$, $p = 0.011$; G2: $W = 0.810$, $p = 0.005$) and did not differ significantly between groups (Mann-Whitney U: $W = 76.0$, G1 as reference group, $p = 0.121$). G2 added a numerically greater number of references (mean = 3.7, $SD = 3.6$; range: 0-14) compared to G1 (mean = 2.0, $SD = 0.8$; range: 1-4).

Spearman correlations between output volume and aggregated quality improvement were non-significant in both groups: word count, $\rho = -0.306$ ($p = 0.268$) in G1 and $\rho = 0.120$ ($p = 0.670$) in G2; and references added, $\rho = 0.087$ ($p = 0.757$) in G1 and $\rho = -0.042$ ($p = 0.883$) in G2. In the combined sample, both correlations approached zero (words: $\rho = 0.011$, $p = 0.953$; references: $\rho = 0.006$, $p = 0.973$). These results indicate that neither producing longer texts nor adding more references was associated with greater quality improvement in either group.

Discussion

This section interprets the findings by evaluating results against the Stylistic Mask Effect. Analysis extends to collaborative writing environments and undergraduate health education. The findings are situated within the pattern of cognitive offloading theory and address broader policy implications. Converging perspectives suggest LLM assistance may enhance language quality in Wikipedia articles. It boosts language quality without improving content depth or source reliability, raising questions about its role in knowledge building.

The hypothesis predicted that LLM assistance would improve language quality without leading to better content depth or stronger references. The findings support this prediction. LLM assistance improved language quality significantly. There were no notable gains in content or references, and scores actually dropped in the LLM-assisted group. This asymmetric effect across the three quality dimensions calls for caution about the benefits of LLM-assisted knowledge production.

Addressing the Study Hypothesis

Editing improvement varied across the three quality dimensions. The Language dimension showed the largest gain. G2 improved by 0.68 (± 0.47), and G1 improved by 0.28 (± 0.57). The group difference demonstrated a statistically significant result ($\beta = 0.400$; $SE = 0.191$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.023$; $p\text{-BH} = 0.068$). The effect size was medium (Cliff's $\delta = 0.400$; 95% CI: +0.004, 0.751). The finding of significant

effect despite limited statistical power (56.2%) suggests the observed Language gain is unlikely to be a chance finding. This tentative conclusion is further supported by the conservative nature of the aggregation measure. Averaging items reduces the group difference when only one item is significantly affected. In this sense, finding a statistically significant effect in this condition provides stronger evidence against a chance explanation.

Content scores showed a small positive trend for the LLM-assisted group. G2 improved by 0.58 (\pm 0.48), and G1 improved by 0.42 (\pm 0.65). The difference was not significant ($\beta = 0.167$; $SE = 0.207$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.214$; $p\text{-BH} = 0.321$; Cliff's $\delta = 0.253$). Reference scores moved in the opposite direction. G2 declined by 0.02 (\pm 0.76), while G1 improved by 0.25 (\pm 0.56). The difference was not significant ($\beta = -0.267$; $SE = 0.243$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.859$; $p\text{-BH} = 0.859$; Cliff's $\delta = -0.164$).

This asymmetric pattern aligns with research on LLM-assisted writing. LLMs are most effective on improving mechanical and stylistic features, such as grammar, vocabulary, and clarity. They have less impact on higher-level components, such as argumentation and knowledge synthesis (Barrot, 2023). Kobak et al. (2025) analysed over 15 million biomedical abstracts. They found that LLM-assisted writing increased the use of style-related verbs and adjectives rather than content nouns. This indicates that the model's contribution operates mainly on the surface level of academic prose.

The Content dimension showed no significant group difference. G2 produced larger mean gains than G1, but the estimate did not reach significance level. This is consistent with evidence that LLM-assisted tasks can show weaker reasoning despite lower cognitive effort (Stadler et al., 2024). Ding et al. (2025) also found that students improved in mechanics and tone, but not in content. For instance, ChatGPT's feedback usually focuses on grammar and punctuation rather than structural or argumentative issues (Alsaedi, 2024).

The References quality score showed no significant group difference, and the point estimate was negative. Although G2 added more references on average (3.7 and 2.0 in G1), the difference was not significant (Mann-Whitney U: $W = 76.0$, G1 as reference group, $p = 0.121$). Variability within G2 was high ($SD = 3.6$; range: 0-14). This suggests inconsistent engagement with source retrieval. A higher quantity of references did not lead to improved quality scores. This pattern is consistent with a known limitation of LLMs. Models generate references that appear credible but may be inaccurate (Barrot, 2023; Chelli et al., 2024; Linardon et al., 2025).

A differential ceiling effect offers an alternative explanation that G2 articles may have had simpler language but stronger content. The results thus might have shown differences in improvement potential, not the impact of LLM usage. Although, this study design makes this unlikely. The study used quota sampling to assign articles based on LiftWing quality tiers. This helped maintain a similar baseline quality across all groups. Pre-intervention scores confirm initial equivalence (see Results).

Content baselines were identical between groups. References baselines were higher in G2, where reduced room for improvement is consistent with the slight decline observed after the intervention. Language baselines were lower in G2, providing more room for improvement. This pattern contradicts a ceiling-effect explanation for the observed advantage. The asymmetric pattern appears not to be explained by baseline ceiling effects.

Stylistic Mask Effect

The dissociation between linguistic polish and substantive quality echoes findings from other research. Scholars have looked at this issue in various ways. This concern connects to several recent ideas: cognitive offloading (Risko & Gilbert, 2016), surface-level processing (Barrot, 2023), the illusion of understanding (Messerli & Crockett, 2024), and the epistemic costs of LLM-assisted academic writing (Tang, 2025).

Each describes how tool-assisted writing can be fluent yet shallow. This dissociation is termed the Stylistic Mask Effect. This study offers this construct primarily as a hypothesis for future research. It suggests that LLM-assisted writing might be better in language quality, but it may not be deeper in content.

The pattern observed in G2 is consistent with this description. Language was smoother, but the use of primary sources and thematic depth did not improve. Kosmyna et al. (2025) report that LLM users show less neural engagement and retain less information. This suggests that tool-facilitated fluency may reduce substantive engagement with the material. Stadler et al. (2024) found that LLM-assisted students wrote with greater fluidity but provided weaker justifications. In this study, the pattern is consistent with the possibility that most G2 participants spent more time editing model-generated text than generating knowledge on their own.

Studies have examined why style and substance diverge in automated writing. Bender et al. (2021) note that these systems generate language from statistical patterns rather than meaning. Their output can sound authoritative while lacking substantive grounding. Messerli and Crockett (2024) warn that automated tools can give a false sense of understanding. This may lead users to believe the text is higher quality than it really is. Hicks et al. (2024), referencing Frankfurt (2005), argue that these outputs lack accuracy with no intent to mislead. Doshi and Hauser (2024) show that these tools boost individual creativity. However, it also reduces collective diversity, leading to a homogenisation of form. The authors compare this to what Jameson called pastiche, an imitation that copies surface styles but lacks the deeper meaning of the original (Jameson, 2005, p. 64-65). These perspectives converge on a shared concern. Linguistic skill might not show real understanding and could hide a profound lack of true knowledge. The Stylistic Mask Effect draws on this research to identify a distinct pattern in collaborative knowledge production.

LLM assistance produced a significant, medium-sized gain in the Language dimension ($\beta = 0.400$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.023$; $p\text{-BH} = 0.068$; Cliff's $\delta = 0.400$; 95% CI: 0.004, 0.751). Data showed no significant gain in Content ($\beta = 0.167$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.214$) or References ($\beta = -0.267$; $p\text{-OLS} = 0.859$). Output volume was not associated with quality improvement in either group (words $\rho = 0.011$; references $\rho = 0.006$). Inter-rater reliability data further support this observed divergence between style and substance. Reliability was lower in G2 ($AC2 = 0.844$) than in G1 ($AC2 = 0.880$), suggesting that the disconnect between polished prose and uneven content made it harder for raters to agree on a final score. Texts that combine LLM generation with uneven substantive editing may produce ambiguous quality signals. This can increase evaluative divergence among reviewers, even when the surface form appears polished. Together, these results describe an asymmetric pattern of linguistic gains without substantive development. Results convergence provides preliminary motivation for the Stylistic Mask Effect as a hypothesis for future testing.

Collaborative Writing Environments

Collaborative platforms such as Wikipedia depend on reliable references and well-developed articles. This study found no significant improvement in either content depth or reference quality attributable to LLM assistance. The References dimension showed a slight decline in G2 and a modest improvement in G1, yet the difference between groups was not statistically significant ($\beta = -0.267$; $p = 0.859$). These findings suggest that LLM assistance yielded no measurable gain in sourcing practices. Source verifiability is central to Wikipedia's editorial model. This null result carries weight for assessing the practical utility of LLM in collaborative knowledge production.

LLMs often struggle to retrieve reliable knowledge or provide verifiable citations. They generate references that often appear credible but may be inaccurate. This limitation is well documented. Confabulation rates in simulated literature reviews can reach 19.9% (Linardon et al., 2025). LLMs do not have automatic access to peer-reviewed or authoritative sources (Chelli et al., 2024). This absence of automated verification increases the burden on volunteer editorial review to ensure citation reliability. This study did not conduct a thorough assessment of confabulated or fabricated references in G2 outputs. LLMs did not boost reference quality, which risks article integrity on Wikipedia, where verifiability remains a core need. Vetter et al. (2025) warn that LLMs pose a risk to Wikipedia's sustainability. They could lower information quality, spread bias, and displace community editors who maintain editorial standards. Huang et al. (2025b) note the increasing detectability of LLM-generated content in Wikipedia edits. This raises concerns about the gradual erosion of the epistemic standards that separate encyclopedic knowledge from automated text.

Stylistic normalisation by LLMs may also erode authorial ownership. The use of model-generated content on Wikipedia raises worries about the encyclopedia's long-term integrity. LLMs trained on

Wikipedia content may create new entries for the platform. This creates a feedback loop that introduces risks to epistemic quality over time. As model-generated text increases in training data, future outputs may reflect patterns based on statistics rather than verified knowledge. Researchers have noted this issue, known as model collapse, in image-generation systems (Shumailov et al., 2024). Unlike human contributors who are subject to peer correction, LLM-generated content lacks the same oversight mechanism. Errors and surface patterns may thus propagate across training cycles without correction.

The Stylistic Mask Effect heightens these risks. Fluent output may reduce reviewer vigilance, allowing weak or poorly sourced content to pass. Monett and Grigorescu (2024) note that exaggerated claims about LLM capabilities can blur the line between fluency and genuine understanding. This is especially serious in health-related articles, where misinformation can affect patient safety. In audiology and hearing health, the accuracy of Wikipedia affects the patients and clinicians who rely on it (Morata et al., 2024; Weiner et al., 2019). These findings urge caution when using LLMs in collaborative knowledge environments. They suggest that editorial policies may need to address the uneven quality of LLM support. A further concern is the potential loss of stylistic diversity, which is part of Wikipedia's epistemic value. LLM-assisted writing tends to produce homogeneous but fluent prose. In this study, G2 showed lower inter-rater reliability than the control group (AC2 = 0.844 and 0.880). This hints that the linguistic polish in LLM-assisted texts may lean towards a generic style instead of true improvement.

Learning Context

Without LLM support, G1 students had more opportunity to connect ideas, check sources, and synthesise themes. They produced an average of 227.8 words and added 2 references, with wide variation (range: 80–436). G2 students had the same 90 minutes and LLM support. Students produced longer texts (mean = 649.7 words) and more references (mean = 3.7), but with high variability (range: 0-14). G2 showed greater improvement in language quality despite the difference in output volume not translating to content or reference gains. One possible explanation is that G2 students spent their time managing model-generated text rather than on independent knowledge work.

These findings add to the ongoing debate on LLM use in education. Supporters highlight the benefits of LLMs for health training. Critics have raised concerns about inaccuracies, fabricated citations, and compromised academic integrity (Rudolph et al., 2023; Sallam, 2023). These concerns are sharper in health education, where source evaluation is essential for clinical practice (Sallam, 2023). Monett and Paquet (2025) warn that uncritical use of LLMs may promote passive learning and commodify education, prioritising output over critical thinking. Our results support this concern, as the increased word count in G2 did not improve content or references, and output volume was not linked to quality

gains. LLMs seem to boost productivity on the surface. However, they do not improve deeper learning without tasks that need source analysis.

Cognitive Models

The pattern of linguistic gains without content or reference gains aligns with cognitive offloading. Reliance on external tools can support task completion while reducing the depth of engagement (Risko & Gilbert, 2016). Participants in G2 focused on editing model-generated text. This likely displaced the effort usually required for independent writing. The absence of any volume-quality link in either group supports this reading. More text and more citations did not deepen engagement. Stadler et al. (2024) found that LLM-assisted students faced lower cognitive demand but produced weaker justifications. Ease of writing does not imply better understanding.

The limited time window likely determined the allocation of effort for G2 participants. Students with LLM access might have prioritised quick writing over checking sources or integrating themes. This pattern is consistent with the high variability in citation behaviour ($SD = 3.6$; range: 0-14), which indicates uneven engagement with source retrieval. Kosmyna et al. (2025) found that LLM assistance reduces neural engagement and content retention. This suggests that LLM-facilitated fluency may decrease ownership and consolidation.

Implications

These findings have important implications beyond the Wikipedia assignment. They provide a perspective on integrating LLM into health education. The study demonstrates that linguistic gains alone do not equate to improved content accuracy or source reliability. On platforms such as Wikipedia, verifiability is paramount. Surface fluency does not ensure quality contributions.

In health education, the shift in cognitive effort raises learning concerns. When students prioritise editing model-generated text over independent knowledge construction, the cognitive work of source verification, conceptual integration, and critical synthesis may be displaced. This displacement risks hindering the development of essential professional skills. Effective patient communication depends on deep understanding and the translation of learned concepts into practice. Clear writing cannot compensate for a lack of authoritative knowledge production.

These findings do not advocate for excluding automated tools from education. Instead, they suggest that pedagogical design could evolve to counteract the Stylistic Mask Effect. Adoption could be guided by tasks that require active engagement with sources and concepts, rather than passive text generation. Educational activities might demand source verification and original synthesis, even when

LLMs are available. The central question is no longer whether these models improve language. It is rather whether their use supports or undermines the core learning objectives of health education.

Limitations and Future Directions

The small sample size and the brief intervention may limit the generalisability of the findings. These factors also prevent a longitudinal assessment of how students adapt to the tool. The post hoc power analysis indicates that the study had enough power to detect large effects but lacked power to identify moderate ones. Read non-significant results with caution, as moderate effects remain possible. Participants were assigned using a random process. Simple randomisation in a small sample overlooked baseline proficiency, past performance, and prior experience with LLMs. This may have introduced uncontrolled variance. All G2 participants received standard training on LLM use. However, their different levels of familiarity might have influenced engagement. Demographic analysis confirmed no significant difference in gender proportions between the groups.

Future research would benefit from addressing several gaps. Studies could control for prior to LLM experience, include direct measures of metacognitive engagement, and assess long-term retention through delayed recall or concept mapping. These measures would clarify how reducing epistemic friction impacts real knowledge building in health education. Larger samples and stratified randomisation would strengthen causal inference. Researchers may also examine how task parameters such as task length, prompting methods, and source-checking requirements influence effort allocation patterns. Current evaluation instruments measure linguistic quality using general criteria but do not distinguish between general fluency and domain-specific communicative adequacy. This distinction is particularly relevant in health such as audiology, where terminology carries specific clinical meanings. Future work could develop domain-specific rubrics that differentiate general writing quality from communicative fitness for specialized health communication contexts.

Conclusion

This study suggests that LLM assistance in Wikipedia editing may produce asymmetric effects on the quality of students' contributions. Its use appeared to improve clarity and style in this sample with a medium-sized point estimate of moderate precision. However, the models did not enhance content depth or reference strength. This pattern suggests a disconnect between the quality of information and its presentation. It supports the concept of a Stylistic Mask Effect in which LLMs obscure gaps in information through fluent prose.

The findings offer preliminary insights for collaborative knowledge environments such as Wikipedia. On these platforms, verifiability and reliable sources are structural prerequisites. Surface-level coherence cannot replace them. Relying on LLMs for text refinement risks substituting meaningful

content with superficial stylistic polish. Surface fluency could cause editors and readers to overlook weakly sourced or inaccurate content.

Integrating LLMs into Wikipedia editing assignments creates a tension between automation and knowledge ownership. Language gains came without content or reference improvements. This is the Stylistic Mask Effect in practice. Education policies and editorial guidelines should aim to prioritise authoritative knowledge over efficiency. Wikipedia editing activities could aim to emphasise source verification, synthesis of ideas, and independent thought. Tasks need active engagement with sources, not passive text generation. This approach can counterbalance the rapid pace of LLM writing. It can also preserve the trustworthiness of collaborative knowledge environments such as Wikipedia.

Ethics Approval. This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculdade de Odontologia de Bauru, Universidade de São Paulo (process no. 6.823.110). All participants provided written informed consent prior to enrolment, in accordance with Resolution 466/2012 of the Brazilian National Health Research Ethics Commission (CONEP).

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Data Availability. Dataset and R statistical analysis code are available in the Zenodo repository (10.5281/zenodo.20320536).

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Author Contributions. Conceptualization: HGCM, LCBJ, JWAW, and KFA contributed to the conception and design of the study. Methodology and Data Curation: HGCM and LCBJ developed the methodology and collected data. Formal Analysis: HGCM performed the statistical and computational analysis. Writing – Original Draft: HGCM. Writing – Review & Editing: HGCM, LCBJ, JAP, JWAW, and KFA read and approved the final manuscript.

AI Use Statement. Hemingway Editor and Proton Lumo (which uses open-source language models) were used for minor language revision. The authors retain full responsibility for the manuscript's content and integrity.

Appendix A

Q1. Content - Thematic Scope - Does the article adequately cover the relevant aspects of the topic?

Excellent: Comprehensive and balanced coverage of the main aspects of the theme

Good: Covers most of the important aspects, with a few gaps

Fair: Covers some aspects, but with significant gaps

Poor: Very limited or insufficient coverage of the theme

Q2. Content - Quality and Accuracy - Is the information accurate, up-to-date, and clearly explained?

Excellent: Accurate, up-to-date, and clearly explained information

Good: Information is generally accurate, with minor inaccuracies or outdated content

Fair: Several inaccuracies or outdated information that compromise quality

Poor: Inaccurate, outdated, or confusing information

Q3. References - Coverage - Is the information provided properly cited?

Excellent: All or almost all important information has references

Good: Most information has references, missing in some points

Fair: Part of the information has references, with important gaps

Poor: Few or no references in the text

Q4. References - Quality - Are the sources used reliable and appropriate?

Excellent: Reliable and appropriate sources (scientific articles, academic books, official institutional websites)

Good: Most sources are reliable, with some sources of moderate quality

Fair: Mix of reliable and questionable sources, or very outdated sources

Poor: Unreliable, inadequate, or absent sources

Q5. Language - Clarity and Correctness - Is the text clear, well-written, and grammatically correct?

Excellent: Clear, fluent text without significant grammatical or spelling errors

Good: Text is generally clear with few errors that do not impair understanding

Fair: Text with limited clarity and several grammatical or spelling errors

Poor: Confusing text with many errors that significantly hinder reading

Q6. Language - Organization of Topics - Is the content organized in a logical and coherent manner?

Excellent: Clear and logical organization, with well-defined sections and appropriate transitions between ideas

Good: Good overall organization, with minor flaws in structuring or transitions

Fair: Confusing organization in some parts, impairing the flow of the text

Poor: Inadequate organization, without a clear structure or with fragmented content

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